

High Resolution Mass Spectrometry Report

Sample Name **NS118**
Comment

Instrument maXis 4G
Method ms_nocolumn_mid_pos.m

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Measured m/z vs. theoretical m/z

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdb	e ⁻ Conf	z
932.4651	1	C 56 H 64 Fe N 10	100.00	932.4661	0.8	0.9	106.9	30.0	odd	1+

Mass list

#	m/z	I %	I
1	173.0783	1.1	10103
2	185.1143	1.2	11424
3	201.1093	4.4	40821
4	205.0596	11.6	108498
5	214.9169	1.0	9259
6	215.1249	1.0	9180
7	217.1042	1.5	13610
8	220.9340	1.2	10855
9	223.0934	0.9	8885
10	226.9510	8.6	80664
11	229.0498	5.5	51260
12	229.1401	1.2	10998
13	238.8834	1.0	9695
14	239.0883	6.9	64414
15	242.9247	1.0	9202
16	243.1350	1.0	9074
17	243.1558	0.9	8739
18	245.0777	1.8	16618
19	251.0522	2.5	23288
20	255.1558	1.3	12137
21	257.0626	1.0	9519
22	261.1297	1.0	9196
23	281.0475	1.4	12992
24	288.9214	5.5	51690
25	290.9246	1.8	16816
26	294.9190	1.0	9399
27	296.2188	1.9	17937
28	301.1402	2.1	19285
29	312.8877	1.1	10501
30	317.2441	1.6	15286
31	319.2598	2.5	22959
32	335.1667	1.0	9271
33	348.9889	1.1	9952
34	350.9864	1.0	9777
35	353.2653	2.9	27251
36	356.9085	1.1	10043
37	360.3226	2.5	23118
38	362.9255	2.2	20154
39	379.1929	1.7	16236
40	381.1002	1.1	10007
41	381.2964	2.2	20206
42	413.2650	1.2	10940
43	423.2191	2.5	23686
44	424.8959	2.9	27427
45	430.9128	2.2	20692
46	439.1237	1.2	11081
47	441.2966	3.9	36629
48	442.2997	1.2	10758
49	443.3331	1.1	10400
50	448.8621	1.5	13706
51	466.2319	4.1	38493
52	466.7333	2.6	24509
53	467.1010	3.6	33726
54	467.2438	3.3	31234
55	468.1016	1.5	14039
56	469.0996	1.0	9602
57	486.8658	1.2	10769
58	487.3594	1.1	10574
59	492.8827	1.6	14833
60	497.3954	1.5	14422
61	498.9005	1.0	9396
62	511.2714	3.0	28324

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#	m/z	I %	I
63	513.1428	2.6	24302
64	513.3692	1.1	10012
65	514.1435	1.1	10286
66	531.3856	1.0	9791
67	536.1641	2.8	26257
68	537.1649	1.4	13220
69	538.1626	1.0	9516
70	541.1197	4.9	45695
71	542.1202	2.5	23387
72	543.1182	1.7	16005
73	553.3881	1.6	15155
74	553.4577	4.4	40892
75	554.4610	1.5	13789
76	555.2975	2.5	23525
77	560.8710	1.5	13670
78	566.8875	1.1	10233
79	569.4315	3.6	33769
80	570.4350	1.3	11950
81	575.4118	1.0	9550
82	599.3237	1.9	17720
83	628.8583	1.3	12312
84	643.3496	1.1	10167
85	685.4337	1.7	15536
86	696.8451	1.2	11463
87	895.4320	2.7	25162
88	896.4348	1.7	15949
89	930.4686	14.2	133053
90	931.4714	9.2	85759
91	932.4025	1.1	10427
92	932.4651	100.0	935335
93	932.8049	1.0	9644
94	932.9554	1.3	12389
95	933.2400	2.1	20092
96	933.4037	0.9	8738
97	933.4680	80.2	750489
98	934.4707	44.4	415192
99	935.4723	9.7	90921
100	936.4741	1.2	11516

Acquisition Parameter

General	Fore Vacuum	2.39e+000 mBar	High Vacuum	9.53e-008 mBar	Source Type	ESI
	Scan Begin	75 m/z	Scan End	2000 m/z	Ion Polarity	Positive
Source	Set Nebulizer	2.0 Bar	Set Capillary	4500 V	Set Dry Gas	8.0 l/min
	Set Dry Heater	200 °C	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V		
Quadrupole	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	4.0 eV				
Coll. Cell	Collision Energy	8.0 eV	Set Collision Cell RF	600.0 Vpp	100.0 Vpp	
Ion Cooler	Set Ion Cooler Transfer Time	75.0 µs	Set Ion Cooler Pre Pulse Storage Time	10.0 µs		